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Research Article

**HEART RHYTHM VARIABILITY IN ESTIMATING THE
CONDITION OF THE ADAPTATION POSSIBILITIES OF THE
CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH II TYPE
DIABETES AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.**

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Abstract:

The increase in mortality from cardiovascular diseases of the population determines the relevance of research aimed at preserving the health of the population, and predicting the course of the pathological process. Coronary heart disease is common in all age groups, causing a high percentage of disability and mortality. Revealing predictors of the condition of patients with ischemic myocardial damage, and especially in combination with comorbidities, improves the quality of treatment by responding to changes in the functioning of the cardiovascular system during the absence of clinical manifestations.

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INTRODUCTION:

The purpose of this work was the mathematical modeling of cardiovascular system functioning of patients with diabetes mellitus and ischemic heart disease based on a heart rate variability.

Heart rate variability makes it possible to measure the functioning of the autonomic nervous system, allows us to estimate the state of the body's regulatory systems, which is especially important if the patient has a combined somatic pathology. The absence of clinical manifestations, especially in the case of diabetic cardiac neuropathy in a patient with diabetes mellitus, increases the risk of developing vascular catastrophes like myocardial infarction, stroke.

We considered 35 indicators of rhythmograms obtained during the daily recording of cardiointervals, including the weighted average rhythmogram variation (WARV). Records were conducted in groups of patients with various functional classes of angina pectoris.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

At the first point of the study, the most informative indicators were selected on the basis of the correlation analysis to build a model of vegetative dysfunction. Statistically significant correlation coefficients with the strongest coupling were selected. To build the model, the expert estimation method was used. Then were calculated weighted coefficients for the selected indicators.

The values of the calculated model are in the range from zero to one and, depending on the obtained model value, a conclusion is made about the state of the adaptive capabilities of the patient's cardiovascular system within the functional class of angina pectoris. In the model developed by us, the normalized values of the indicators are substituted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Criteria of functioning of the developed model presented on table 1.

Table 1. Criteria of functioning of the developed model.

The normalized value of the indicator	
unsatisfactory level	0,7-1
satisfactory level	0,333-0,69
good level	0-0,332

Prognostic model of the heart rate variability index of SVVR in patients with I FC angina pectoris. SDNN ind (the correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.58), NN50 (the correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.77), PNN50 (the correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal

to 0.78), RMSSD (correlation coefficient reliable and equal to 0.62).

Expert ranking of indicators presented on tables 2, 3, 4. $WARV = f(SDNN\ ind, NN50, PNN\ 50, RMSSD)$

Table 2. Expert ranking of HRV indicators in patients with angina pectoris FC I.

Indicator	Expert estimates							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
SDNN ind	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2
NN50	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	3
PNN50	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	1
RMSSD	2	3	3	3	2	3	2	3

$$WARV\ 1\ group = 0.353 * SDNNind + 0.24 * NN50 + 0.24 * PNN50 + 0.176 * RMSSD (1)$$

Prognostic model of the index of heart rate variability of SVVR in patients of the second group. As indicators, PNN50 (correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.74), RMSSD

(correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.72), SDSD (correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.76) were selected. $WARV = f(PNN50, RMSSD, SDSD)$

Table 3. Expert ranking of HRV indices in patients with angina pectoris FC II.

Indicator	Expert estimates							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PNN50	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
RMSSD	2	3	3	2	1	1	3	2
SDSD	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

$$\text{WARV 2 group} = 0.516 * \text{PNN50} + 0.226 * \text{RMSSD} + 0.258 * \text{SDSD} \quad (2)$$

Prognostic model of the index of heart rate variability of WARV in patients of the third group. SDNN (correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.42), NN50 (correlation coefficient is

statistically reliable and equal to 0.71), PNN 50 (correlation coefficient is statistically reliable and equal to 0.52) were selected as indicators.

$$\text{WARV 3 group} = f(\text{SDNN}, \text{NN50}, \text{PNN 50})$$

Table 4. Expert ranking of HRV indices in patients with III FC angina pectoris.

Indicator	Expert estimates							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
SDNN	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1
NN50	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2
PNN 50	3	2	2	1	2	3	3	2

$$\text{WARV 3 group} = 0.4332 * \text{SDNN} + 0.366 * \text{NN50} + 0.2 * \text{PNN50} \quad (3)$$

Model values presented on table 5.

Table 5. Model values

Model values	
norm	0..0,333
intense adaptation	0,34..0,666
breakdown of adaptation	0,67..1

CONCLUSION:

The models of the state of the adaptive capabilities of the cardiovascular system developed by us were tested in clinical conditions and showed high accuracy in determining.

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